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Termite mound impact on soil properties

Termites are one of the dominant groups of soil macrofauna in the tropics. Termites belong to the order Isoptera, a group of cellulose-eating insects that build mounds to live. The structure of the termite mounds is complicated and has an extensive system of tunnels. There is a variety of shapes and sizes. The mound is constructed by the soil, termite saliva and dung. Though the mound appears to be in definite structure, it is porous in nature. Termite mounds can be observed in common fields may have a good source of nutrition. There are some evidences for the available plant nutrients in the soil, which are discussed hereunder:

Termites play a central role in the functioning of these ecosystems by regulating the distribution of natural resources such as water and nutrients. Termites are essentially detritivores, feeding on a wide range of dead plant material at various stages of decomposition. The utilization of such a wide range of food resources has been made possible by the close association with microbial symbionts in both gut and nest. As a consequence of a diet comprised entirely of autotrophically fixed carbon, they can exert a significant effect on carbon mineralization and nutrient recycling, especially where termite biomass is high, as in some tropical areas.

The nature of their parent materials largely determines the chemical properties of soils, but with additional influence from climate, vegetation cover and the activities of soil organisms, especially for older soils (Holt and Lepage, 2000). Termites use nutrient-rich salivary secretions and faecal material as cementing agents in construction. In some regions where termite activity is high, they can significantly modify soil chemical properties. Because of its higher clay content and usually higher exchangeable cation concentration, the translocation of soil from deeper to the surface during termite gallery and mound construction may also enrich the surface soil with nutrients useful to plants

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Profile development

The mound building and gallery construction activities of termites in and on the soil significantly affect the structure and composition of soil profiles. The predominant termite-mediated processes causing profile modification are: 1) translocation of sub-surface soil to the surface, 2) microped structure and 3) creation of subsurface galleries.

Physical properties

The behaviour of termites in repacking soil, augmented with organic material derived from salivary and faecal products, during the construction of mounds and galleries has a marked effect on the physical properties of these constructions (Lee and Wood, 1971). Their subterranean galleries and chambers also influence soils' porosity and water-holding characteristics and under certain conditions, affect infiltration rates. In the case of soil feeding termites, although their galleries do not usually lead to the soil surface, they are numerous in the upper 200 mm of the soil profile. Where termite activity is high, the presence of galleries may significantly affect the hydraulic properties of the soils. Although there is less information on the effects of termites on the hydraulic properties of soils, the combined nest-building and foraging activity of termites in many tropical ecosystems is thought to have a considerable influence on their physical properties.

Chemical properties

In addition to altering the physical properties of soils, construction activity by termites often results in changes to the chemical properties of soils. Physical alterations primarily cause such changes via incorporating cation rich clay sub-soils into termite constructions and incorporating, or deposit of, organic rich faecal and salivary material into these constructions. Subsequent erosion of the mound material then provides the surface soil with additions relatively enriched in nutrients. Most research to date has shown that termite mound material contains significantly higher concentrations of the exchangeable cations Ca, Mg, Na, and K than adjacent soils. This enrichment has occurred because many species select particles from clay rich horizons within the soil profile to construct their mounds. Clay minerals present in termite mounds are mostly thought to have been derived from deeper parts of the soil profile although neo-formation by termite action has also been suggested as a possible origin for some minerals. The organic matter composition of termite mounds is influenced by the feeding habits of termites and concentrations are usually 2-5 times higher than that of the surrounding surface soil. The raised organic matter content of mound soil N and P is at a higher level.

Biological properties

Termite mound soil is similar to the soil from which it is constructed in that it usually contains large numbers of microorganisms. These microorganisms, predominantly fungi

and bacteria, have various functions within the organic matter decomposition process (Adebajo, *et al.*,2021) The association between termites and fungi can be divided into two types, non-mutualistic and mutualistic. Non-mutualistic associations usually occur between dry wood termites and certain wood rotting fungi, with evidence suggesting that wood previously attacked by fungi is more palatable to these termites. Termite mound soil contains some useful bacteria capable of solubilizing phosphate and potassium and producing indole acetic acid, which are the plant growth-promoting potentials and suppress plant soil pathogen. It is evident from the three-fold increase in yield that plant growth is enhanced by termite mound soil (Rajagopal,1983).

Conclusion

Termite mound soil has a good source of plant nutrients and contributes to yield increase. The presence of organic matter, soil enzymes and rich microbial diversity in the

termite mound soil helps to hasten the composting process of residues present in the soil. The farmers cultivating in sandy soils can enhance soil nutrient content through the mixed application termite mound soil with any organic manures and crop rotation with the legume crops. Further studies to explore the possibility of using termite mound soil as a nutrient source for crop production will help the farmers to utilize the termite mound soil in productive ways.

References

- Adebajo, S.O., Akintokun, P.O., Ezaka, E. 2021 Use of termitarium soil as a viable source for biofertilizer and biocontrol. *Bull Natl Res Cent* **45**, 100
- Holt, J.A., Lepage, M. (2000). Termites and Soil Properties. In: Abe, T., Bignell, D.E., Higashi, M. (eds) *Termites: Evolution, Sociality, Symbioses, Ecology*. Springer, Dordrecht.
- Lee, K.E. and Wood, T.G. (1971) *Termites and Soils*. Academic Press, London.
- Rajagopal.D (1983) Effect of termite mound soil on plant growth, *Tropical Pest Management*,29:2, 194-195, DOI: 10.1080/09670878309370798